

Original Article

Training Needs of Basic School Teachers in Agra & Firozabad District of Uttar Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

The teacher occupies a very important place in society because he brings about the transfer of the values and tradition from one generation to next. He maintains the level of technological skill and keeps the light of civilization burning bright. He is expected to help in the level of social revolution that is taking place in the country. His duty does not end in the classroom with his students. He should be able to constantly adjust his methods and approach to suit the changing times. Teachers need training for better results to students and society. Need of training for primary and secondary teachers have been emphasized by many educational commissions/committees, therefore this study has been conducted to know the training needs of basic schools teachers.

INTRODUCTION

The world continues to experience constant change. There being unprecedented upheavals in the political, social and economic domains. International global revolution in information and communication systems and rapid astonishing technological advance are influencing all nation and regions of the world. This likely to continue unabated were into the 21st century. In the light of such change, countries in the regions throughout the world are undertaken a critical reassessment of their education system. Education is seen as pivotal in dealing successfully with these changes, facilitating economic development, social cohesion, peace and tolerance.

According to John F. Kennedy, One of the ways to get the best education is to have the best trained teachers. The teacher is a great force in building future citizen and improving the young generation. The teacher is just like a gardener. He alone has the privilege to train up a child in the way; he will not depart from it. Children are hopes of tomorrow. They are the citizen and teachers. Yet the progress and future of education, its system, its quality and ideals will depend upon how any by whom they are educated.

India has celebrated its 65th year of independence with joy and vigour. Literacy rate of India is 74.04%. (India Census 2011) In various states its level is not equal. The main cause of illiteracy is the non-availability of adequate trained teacher of grass root that is primary level. Children's are future of a nation. So, primary education is also the stepping stone in the making of good citizen. Now days less attention should be paid for training of primary teachers.

NEED OF THE STUDY

- The major reason for in-service education is to promote the continuous improvements of the total professional's staff of school system. All teacher, including administrators must constantly study in order to keep up with advance in subject matter and in theory and practice of teaching continuous in-service educational in needed to keep the teacher, abreast of new knowledge and to take them to realize their experience and through effects.
- Another purpose of in-service education programmes is to give much needed help to teachers who are entering a new responsibility or a new field of work within the profession. Such people need various answers and in such academic programmes, we can answer their questions.
- In-service education must be eliminating deficiencies in the background preparation of teacher and other professional workers in education. Many have not been able to complete their training with satisfactory results. We can help their knowledge more through and

deep. The constant and continual social changes which create need for curriculum among call upon the authorities to give a fresh training to teachers through in service education programme and also familiarizes them the need curriculum. Teacher training colleges are not the end of all teacher education. Some of the teachers through trained, need further training. This is more so in case of special subject teacher. To supplement the pre-service training in-service training education is very necessary.

- In-service education provides opportunity to the teacher to learn new skill in practical workshop. In-service education programmes provide a platform to the teachers for sharing of their ideas. They can exchange ideas and view among themselves and find the common problem. They are facing at the time of delivering lesson.
- It has remarked that sometimes in-service education plugs the leakage in teaching profession. It makes teaching profession attractive one. It also gives opportunity to teacher, for their professional growth. Lastly, it makes the work educational reconstruction easier. It helps in bringing in “Living Touch” with our subject. It is based on the concept of learning society.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Objectives of the present study are following –

1. To identify the training needs of basic school teachers in the different areas of languages.
2. To know the training needs of basic school teachers, for teaching gifted/talented students.
3. To find the training need of basic school teachers for effective teaching of Math.
4. To identify the training needs of basic school teachers for conducting and demonstrating science experiments and operating computer.
5. To find out the training needs of basic school teachers for educating the masses about family planning, performing on selection duty, acting as census enumerator, conducting village survey.
6. To know the training needs of basic school teacher for organising co-curricular activities, games and sports, cultural, religious and national festivals.

SAMPLE

200 primary school teachers working in U.P. Government Basic Schools of Agra (100) and Firozabad (100) constituted the sample of the present study. The teachers were selected on purposive basis.

TOOL

In present study, a self-prepared questionnaire consists used for assessing the training needs of primary school teacher. This questionnaire consists 25 items. Preparing the final draft of questionnaire a major survey was conducted of basic school of Agra and Firozabad districts to identify the training need of primary school teachers.

COLLECTION OF DATA

For the present study, the data was collected by the administering the self-developed questionnaire on 200 teachers working in government basic school of Agra and Firozabad district of Uttar Pradesh.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

After collection of data tables are made for the process of analysis. Percentage was calculated for analysis and interpretation.

MAIN FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. 62% teachers indicated that they wanted that they wanted training in Hindi, 44% feel the need of training on Environmental Studies, and 70% teachers indicated the need of training in the subject of Mathematics, whereas 74% of the teachers wanted in the subject of English.
2. 48% teachers responded that they wanted training in Hindi word composition, 59% wanted training in Hindi sentence making and 34% teachers felt the need of training in the knowing word meaning in Hindi Language.
3. 73% teachers responded that they wanted training in Hindi spelling. 42% wanted training in Hindi Grammar and 24% teachers felt the need of training in the Calligraphy in Hindi Language.

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4. 56% teacher responds that they wanted training in Intonation of speaking Hindi, 70% wanted training in Pronunciation, and 40% teachers felt the need of training in Accent for improving in Hindi Language.
5. 65% teachers were of the view that they should be given training in order to know more about environmental studies.
6. 80% teachers responded that they wanted training in Special Categories of learners like Deaf/Dumb/Blind, whereas 45% wanted to be trained for the teaching of Gifted and Creative students.
7. 43% teachers responded to be trained for conducting and demonstrating Science Experiments, and 25% of the teachers also wanted training for Operating of a Computer.
8. 55% teachers needed training for organizing meetings of PTA's.
9. 35% teachers wanted to be trained for OHP, 25% of the teachers were interested to get training in order to know the use of Film Projector, and 27% teachers wanted training for the use of use Slide Projector.
10. 80% teachers wanted training for football, kho-kho and other games.
11. 54% teachers wanted training for Drama and Dance, 40% teachers wanted training for songs and debate.
12. 60% teachers wanted training for educating the masses for application and adoption of small families/family planning measures.
13. 47% teachers wanted training for preparation of Model and Diagram, 34% wanted training for Preparation of charts, Pamphlets and Posters etc.
14. 32% teachers wanted training for knowing more about different national festivals and 35% wanted training for knowing more about different religions.
15. 60% teachers wanted training for population education, and 38% wanted training for environmental education.
16. 35% teachers wanted training in distribution of Mid-day meal, 37% wanted training in maintenance, and 54% wanted training in record keeping of Mid-day meal.
17. 37% teachers wanted training in physical education training to students.
18. 48% teachers wanted training for first aid training.
19. 58% teachers wanted training for understanding school administration, preparation of examination results and forming Time-table.
20. 51% teachers wanted training in evaluation techniques.
21. 48% teachers wanted training for understanding child psychology so as to become a successful teacher.
22. 42% teachers wanted training for identifying and teaching talented/creative students.
23. 45% teachers wanted training in guidance and counselling techniques.
24. Some teachers listed number of areas/fields in which they felt immediate need of training, training about knowing the child behaviour, training about psychology, training about discipline maintain, training about vocational, training about various languages etc.

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